

Supplementary Information for

'Lineage-Specific Evolution, Structural Diversity, and Activity of R2 Retrotransposons in Animals'

By

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Supplementary Figure 1

Figure S1: Structural arrangements of R2 N-termini to classify folds of novel protein conformations. (a) R2 structural references of the N-termini studied from R2 cryo-EM structures of complexes bound to the same DNA substrate, including A lineage (R2Tg - TaGu, R2Pm - PlaMe) by our group [1] and D lineage (R2Bm - BoMo) by others [2]. Three R2 N-termini are superimposed on each other and each box highlights the structural regions that best align. Coloured squares below each domain represent the matching colours for

each R2 reference (TaGu is green, PlaMe is yellow, and BoMo is purple). Top panel: ZnFs across elements can be aligned, with the exception of BoMo which only has ZnF1. Bottom panel: Myb domain requires a local alignment to confirm similar fold architecture containing three expected alpha helices connected by two loops. (b) Conformation of Ctenophore ZnF1-Myb bound to DNA relative to R2 lineages using BoMo (D lineage, top panel) and PlaMe (A lineage, bottom panel) as structural references. All ctenophores examined (n=4) with AlphaFold (AF) predictions, BMi as the representative shown, have a D-lineage-like Myb conformation, where Myb is spatially closer to the RT domain. (c) A structural representative (AF structure) of independently folded ZnFs where ZnF2-ZnF4 (boxed) do not co-fold. (d) Two orientations of an AF structure for BFo showing a distinct fold arrangement where ZnF2-ZnF4 (boxed) have shorter connections between them than model R2s in (a).

Supplementary Figure 2

>Bfo_R2_shifted_from_R2_targetsite

MEEKNNETAGRTASSDKTSKSSASGSAARAAVTPAPSRACLFCKAFKLRGLAGHTRRCESNPEWLNEKIHSSRWDFSGRSPVNCARCDLHMKATCYIGHFPDCIATNGCFRCGNQV
 PVADYVEHFQVCVVRTIDPAEPPTQVVIPEVQKVTCPYCPAALQAKFSFKPGRGLSMHVKKKHPKEWNDYQLNRMELYPSQYIWRGDDDELICQAIIEEYQSSAPAVKKAFGINQFIQ
 FRSPHCTLDSITCHRKTSFKEYAKDRAKRIADQQAESAEEESLPNEDGGHFEEVEILSEKEKSAIAAKPFGSEILEIHQHLVNRWDTACSAAKLVFEELTCKFGKPNIPVHK
 VKQGADPRPPGKPTRKSKKRANRRRLKPSKEKRRESYAKVQKRWSKKRVDVKSILDGKLEQVQGEKPTMEKQHDYWKSLFERPSPEDPGKVPGESSVQYELSAPLTKEEVANGLG
 TAKEASTGPDGVPLSALKELGSLWVLYCALWMMKSETPKGWRVSRVTLIDKTADECGKNPEDFRPISSSYFYRIYARSISSRLTRAVPISKRQRFIRQDGVDRNIELFDNLVKD
 AKRTLTPLSVAFMDIRKAFDSVGHASIQRALEWAGVPGRVRRVIEELYDCYTEVGGGRIRVNRGVKQGDPLSSFLFNIVLEMALSRVPPGLGINYLGHQLFYMAFADDMILLARNA
 HVLQRIVDMVSSELGLAGLEFNHAKCKVLSLVTDPNKAISMIDTVEIAVNGDRIPPLGVLDTYRYLGDVGVKGVKPFEPQKELKDLLQRLTKAPLKPQRLYALRVHTMPRFQHK
 LIFSKVTRNALSQMDSLVRKHVREWLKLPDDVTKAALYADVSGGGLGLICLERRVPLKYSRIERLRDSDDELVRLIDQEQVNKRVMQWKDRCKMSGKTYRSKEELRDLYRTQLNS
 TVDGGIRGDRGLRSLMRSVGPICLPTTRYIHAINVRLGTLQTSERKARGRVCNENGLCDKERACHARKAVATLGHISQVCPVVHGLRVRRHDRVDRVANQLQSRKKSVEKV
 LVEKTIKLDQGTVLRPDIIIVLTDTSIEVIDVQIKADMGIRRDLETDQAKRAKYDRGDVQTSIERELSVVMGRLYVTALTITFRGQLPRHTVDLTRLKFKTLLPELVADVLADT
 GSMFVVWHRTTGNAGKP

```

Bfo      -----MEEKNNETAGRTASSDKTSKSSASGSAARAAVTPAPSRACLFCKAFKLRGL
Bmi      -----
MLe      KLHRCCPLFQEKDSGGLNRSAS-----GV
PBa      TL----PFLKLNMRNLNNEKNS-----GA
  
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```

Bfo      AGHTRRCESNPEWLNEKIHSSRWDFSGRSPVNCARCDLHMKATCYIGHFPDCIATNGCF
Bmi      -----KNTMFNITPR---PEDSQVDRVTIDAESGLPNHAGANLLQCE
MLe      MSNTSHSKLNLK-MDNKLTSLKETPSGV---RADIITRVRTSSNRG-EHNSGVTYPRCE
PBa      VRSTEFVS----ADNRPSQSLRTTESH-----RCP
          :
          *
  
```

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Bfo      RCGNQ-VPVADYVEHFQVC-----VRTIDPAEPPTQVVIPEVQKV-TCPYCPAA
Bmi      WCDRLCKNKAGLTLHKRACKNNPAVGSSAGNTDNRRIINTP----PTMRSLFNCEYC---
MLe      -----QGVAPLDTHGGICDAPPQVTPATETDKQKK-----CEYC---
PBa      NCRKLCRSGNGLALHMKHC-----AKCYQNGDNRQEPVK----PRM----ECSIC---
          * * . . . * *
  
```

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Bfo      LQAKFSFKPGRGLSMHVKKKHPKEWNDYQLNRMELY-PSQYIWRGDDDELICQAIIEEYQS
Bmi      ---NTGYGTRGLSAHISKKHIPEWNNIKMERFKADGPRQHVWREGDWEILCQGEETHDR
MLe      ---EFTYLKPRQIGTHMRKRHPQEWNDIKRTKFLSE-KRQKRWLEDFELLIGQEYLV
PBa      ---GLFFSGQRGVAIHKRKKHPAEWNETKRVEDTLS-RKKIRWTSGDRELLHGMIEWEA
          : * :. * *:* *** : . : * . * *:: . *
  
```

Figure S2: (Top) Translated R2 ORF from *B. forskalii*. (Bottom) Multiple sequence alignment of all Ctenophora (*Bolinopsis microptera*, *Pleurobrachia bachei*, *Mnemiopsis leidyi* (recurated from Kojima et al. 2016) and *Beroe forskalii*.) R2 N-terminal ZnFs. CXXC residues in the ZnFs are highlighted in green.

Supplementary Figure 3

>WFMF01000099.1:20329-29541 *Beroe forskalii* isolate Bf201606 sca99

AATAGGACTTTGGTCTTATTTTGGTGGTTCCGAGACCGAAGTAAATGATTAAATAGGGACAGTTGGGGCCATTGCTATTTTCATTGTCAGAGGTGAAATTTGGATTTATGAAAGACGAACCTTCGCAAAAGCATTG
GCCAAGGATGTTTTTCATTAATCAAGAACCAGGTTGGAGGCTCGAAGACGATCAGATACCGTCTAGTTCACCAACATAAACAGTACCGCTGCGGATCGGAGTGCCTAACGTAAGGCTCCTTCGGCACGCTATGA
GAAATCAAGACTTCGGTTCCGGGGGAGATGTTCCGAAGAATGAACTTAAGGAAATGACGGAAGGCCACCACAGGAGTGAACCTGCGGTTAATTTGACTCAACACGGGAAAACTCACCAGGTCAGAC
ATAGGAAGGATTACAGCATTTAGAGCTCTTTCTGATTCTATGGGCTGGTGCATAGCCGCTTCTTAGTTGGTAAAGAGATTTGCTGGTTAATTCGCTAACCGAACGAGACCTTAACCTGCTAAATAGTACAGC
GTTATTTAACCGTGGTCACTTCTTAGAGGGACTATCGCTTCAAAGCGATGGAAGTTGAGGCAATAACAGGCTGTGATGCCCTTAGATGTTCTGGGCCACACGCGTTACACTGATGAAGCCAGCGAGTAT
ATCGCCTTACCAGAAAGGTCGGGTAATCTTGGAAACTTTATCGTCTGGGATAGACCTTTGCAATATTGGTCTTAAATCGAACCATCTAGTACCTGTTCCCTCGAAGTTCCCTCAGGATAGCAGGAG
CTCATTTCCAGTTTTATCAGGTAAGCGAATGATTAGAGCCCTTAGGGATGAACATCCTTAACTTATCTCAAACCTTTAAATGGTAAAGATGTCGACTTGCTTAATTTGAAGCCGGCCACGAATGGGAGCTCT
AGTGGCCATTTTTGGTAAGCAACTGGCGATGCGGGATGAACCGAACGTTTGGTTAAGCCGCTAAATCGACGCTCATCAGATCCCAAAAGGTGGTGGTATATAGCACAGCAGGACGGTGGCCATGGAAGT
CGGAATCCGCTAAGGAGTGTGAACAACCTCACCTGCCAATCAACGACCCGAAAAATGGATGGCCTCAAGCGTCTGCTTATACCAGACCTTTGAGCAAAATGCTAAGCTCGGACGAGTAGGAGGCGTGGGG
TCGTGAAGAAGCTCTGGGCTGAGCCTGGGTCACAGCCCTAGTGCAGATCTTGGTGTAGTACAAATATCAAATGAGAACCTTTGAAAGCCGACGCTGGAGAAGGGTTCCATGTGAACAGCAGTTGACCTGG
GTTAGTCGATCCTAAGAGATAGGAAACTCCGTGTTAAAGTCCCGATCTACGACTCAGCTCACTCCGGGCCCTATCGAAAGGGAATCGGGTAAATTTCCCAAGCCGAATGGGGGATTCTGTCTTCCGGGA
CAGAATTCGGCTAACGCAACACTGGAGACTGCGGATGCAACCGAACGTTTGGTTAAGCCGCTAAATCGACGCTCATCAGATCCCAAAAGGTGGTGGTATATCCGAGATATGGTTAGCTGTGTAAGACAGCCG
CTTCTTGGTGGTTCCTGCCCTCCGATGGCCCTGAAAAATCCAGGGAGAGAATAAACTCTCATCCGGTCTGACCAATAACCGCAGCAGGCTCCAAGGTTAACAGCCTCTGGTCGATAGACAAATGTAGGTA
AGGGAAGTCGGCAAAATAGATCCGTAACCTCGGAAAAGGATTTGGCTCAAGGGTTGGGCTGTGGGCTGACAGCCGACAGCTCGAAAGCCTTGGTGGACTGTAGATGAAGTTCCCGAGCTCCGATGGG
CGTCTCGGATCGAGGAGGAGGCTGCAGCTTCTGCTCCGGACATTTCCGACAGCAGCTAAACCAACTTAGAAGTGTACGGACAAGGGGAATCCGACTGTAAATTTAAACCAAGCATTCGATGGCCGGAA
ACGGTGTGACGCAATGTGATTTCTGCCAGTGCCTGAAATGTCAAAGTGAAGAAATTAACCAAGCCGGGT***CCTTAAATTTGGAATCGAAGAAGTGGGACATATGAGAAGGGAGAAT**

Shift in insertion site

GAACGCTGACTTAGGCAAGAAAGTTGAGATGGAACGAAGTAAAGAGTGTGACCCTTCTTCCCTCCAGCGAGTCACTGATACTTGTTCTTTAAGCCCTTGACGAAGTAAAGATGAATACCTTTATACGTTATTGT
CATTTAGATGCGAGACAAGGCTGCGAGCAAGACAAGGCAAGCAATAGACCGTGGGTCTGATACCAGTGACACCAGGGAAAAAGAAAAAATGTCATCTCGTGAAGGTTATTTATTTTGGTACGGCCGGAG
AGATAGACGGCCAGGTCTAACCGTACAGGTCCGGCCACGACGTTGCTGTCAACGGAATTTGCTTAAAGGAAAGTCCCAATCTCGTCTCAACAGCGGAACCGGCTGTAGAGTGCACATGGGCAATGTGCAAC
CTCATGACAATCTCCGCTCAGATGCTTCTCGGGTATGCGAAAAACAGAGTGAAGGGGCTAGTAGGCTTGTGGGCTCATCTCTTATTTAACAAAGTGAAGAAAAAATAAGTGAAGTGCACCGTGGCAAC
GCTAGCAGTGATAAAACAGCAAGAGCTCGGGCTCAGGTTTCTAGCTGCACGCGGCTGTGACTCTCGACCCAGTAGAGCTTGGCTCTTCTGTTGAAGCCCTTTAAACTCAGAGGCTGGCGGGACACAGCGGTA
GATGCGAGTGAATCCTGAATGGTTGAACGAGAAAAATTCATAGCTCCAGTGGGACTTCACTGGTATGATCGCCGTAACCTGCGCTGTTGATCTCATATGAAGCCACATGTTATATCGGGCACTTTCCGGA
TTGACTCGGACTAACGGATGCTCCGATGTGGAATCAAGTCCCGTGGCTGATTATGTTGAGCATTCAAAGTTTGTGGTGAAGCAGTATGATCCCGCTGAACCAACCCACAGGTTGTTATACCTGAGGTA
CAGAAGTGGACGCTGCCCTTATGCCCCGCTGCTCTTCAAGCTAAATTTAGCTTAAACCTTGGCGGAGCCCTTCAATGTCATGTTCAAGAAAGACCCCTAAAGAGTGAATGATTACCACTGAACAGGATGGAAC
TTTACCCTCCAGTACATCTGGCGGAGGTTGACGATGAAGTATTTGCCAGGCGATCGAGGAGTATCAGTCTCAGCTCCCGCGTTAAAAGGCGTTTGGCATCAATCAGTTTATCCAATCAGATCTTCCC
ACATTGCACCTTTCACAGCATAACTGTGTCACAGGAAAATCTTCTTTTAAAGAAATATGCGAAAGACCGAGCCAAACGCATAGCTGATCAACAGGCTGTGGCTGAGTCAAGGCGGAAGAGTCACTCCCAACGAG
GATGGAGGCCACTTCGAAGAGTGAAGATACTCTGAGAAGGAAAAATCGCCACTCGTCCAAACCTTTGGCAGTGAATTTGAGATCCATCAGCATCTGTGAACAGGAGATGGGATACAGCATGTAGTG
CAGTAAGTGTAGTCTTGAAGAGCTTACTTTGAAGTTTCGGAAGAGCTAATTTCCCGGCTTAAAGTGAAGGTTTAAAGGTAAGGTTTACAGGCTTCCAGGGAAAAAACCCACAGCCGATTTAAAGAGGCAATAG
CGCAGGACTCAAGCCAGCAAGGAAAAAGGAAAGTTATGCAAGGACAGAGAGGTGAGCAAGAAAAAGGTTGAGCCTCAATCTATCTTTGACGCGAAATTTGAGCAAGTACAAGGAGAAAAACCA
ACGATGGAGAAGCAGCAGCTACTTGAAGAGTCTGTTGAAAGGCCAGTCCGTAAGTAAAGTCCCGGGGAAAAAGTTAGTACAATATGAATTTGAGTGTCCGCTGACGAAAGGAGAGGTAGCCAACG
GCTTAGGAACAGCAAGAGGCCCTCGACCCGACAGATGGGTTCTCTCTCGCTTAAAGGAACTTTGGTTCCTTAGTCTGTTGGTCTGACTGTGCGTGTGATGAAGTGGAAAACTCCGAAGGTTGGAG
GTTAGCTGAGTCTTACTAGCTAGGAATTTGAGCAAGACAGGCGGAGCAATGTGGAAAAACCCGGAGGCAATTTGAGGTAAGGTTTGAAGTAAAGGTTTAAACACGCTTAAAGGTTGAGGTTGAGGCAAGCA
GTTCAATCTCGAAAAAGACAGCGTGGATTCAATGGAAGATGTTGTGACAGACAATATGCAATGTTTGCATATTTGGTCAAGGACGCAAGGCAACTTAAACCCCTTGAGCGTGGCCTTTATGGATATAAGGA
AGGGCTTTGACAGTGTGCGCACCGGAGTATTCAGGCTGCCCTGGAATGGGCTGGTCCCTGGTGGGAGAGGCTCATCGAGGAATATACAGGAGCTGATACAGGAGTTGAGGGGGGAGGATTCGTG
GAACAGAGGGGTAAGCAGGTTGACCCGCTGAGCTCCTTCTTGTTCATATAGTTCTCGAGATGGCACTCAGTAGATTCCACCAGGCTGGGCATCAACTATCTGGGGCATCACTGTTTTACATGGCCTTCGCT
GATGATGATGTTCTTACTAGCTAGGAATTTGAGCAAGACAGGCGGAGCAATGTGGAAAAACCCGGAGGCAATTTGAGGTAAGGTTTAAAGGTTTGAAGTAAAGGTTTAAACACGCTTAAAGGTTGAGGTTGAGGCAAGCA
GGAATAAAGCGAGTATGATAGACTGACGCTGAGATAGCGGTAACCGTGTGATGATATCCACCCTCGGGGTTGGTACCTATCGTTATCTAGGATAGAGCTCGGAGTGAAGGGATTCCCAAAATCGAAC
GCAGAAGGAACTAAAGACTTGCTTCAGAGACTCAGAAAGCAGCCTTGAACCAACATACAGCGGCTATAGCCCTGAGAGTTCACACCATGCCGATTCAGCACAAGCTTATCTTTGAAAGTAACTAGGAAC
GCTCTAAGCCAAATGGACTATTAGTCAAGAAAGCAGTAAAGAGTGGCTCAAATACCCGAGCTGTACCAAGGCCGCGCTGACGCGGAGCTTTGGGCTGGAGGATTGGGCTCATCTGCTCGAACGAAAGG
TACCCCTCGTAAATTTTCGAGGATGGAAGATTTACCGCAATCTGATGACAGCAACTGATCCGATTTGTAACCAAGAACAGGTGAACAGCAGGTGATGCAATGGAAGTCCGTTGAAGATGAGTGGCAAGCA
CTATCGTAGTAAAGAGGAGCTCAGGATCTGTATAGAACCAATGAATCCACAGTGTGATGGGAAGGTTAAGGGAGATACCCGGCTAGGACAGTATCGATGCGGTCGCTGTTGAGCCCTGCATCCACTC
ACTCCAACCTAGATACATCCATGCTATAAACGTTTCGCTTGGAACCTACAGACTTCGAGAGAAAGCCAGAGGAGGTTGCAACGAGAAGCAGCGCTCTATGTGACAAAGAGAGGCAATGTACGCTAGGAAAG
CTGTTGCAACTTAGTGCATATATCTCAAGTATGCCGTAGTACAGGCTCAGAGTGAAGAGCAGCAGCAGTAAAGAGCCGTTGTTGCCAACCTGACAGAGCAGAAAAAGTCTGTTGAGAAAGTACTGGT
TGAGAAGAGCATAAAACCTCCAGGATGGTACTGCTGAGACCGGACATCAATGTTCTCACTGACACTTTCTAATGAGGTTATTGATGTCAAATAAAGGCTGATATGGGAATCCGAGGGGACCTCGAGCCGACCA
ACCGCAAAAGAGGCAAGTACGACAGGGGCGAGTACAACATCGATAGAAGTGAATTTGCGGTGGTGGGATGGGAGGCTGTATACAGTACGGCTTGACAATCACGTTTACAGGGGAGCTGCCAAGACACA
CAGTTGATCTGGCTACGCGTCTTAAATTAAGACGCTATTGCCAGAACTAGTGGCTGACGCTTGGCAGACAGGCTAGTATGTTTGTGGTCTGGCACAGGACAGCGGAAACCGAGGAAACCGTAGATGCCCTT
GTCTTAGGATAGAAAAAGTCCCCCTCTGCTACATCATCAGGAGGCCAGGACGCAATAGTACAGTAGGCTGGTGTGTTTACCATCAACGTAAGGAGAACGTTGCTAGTATCTCCACCTACTGCATAAAAT
GGAACCTGATTCCAGCAGGATGAGTTTGACTTGCACACGAGGCTCACAGCTTAGTATGATGAGTTTGAACCGCATGATGACGGTGTATGCACTGTGATGATCTGAAGTCTGCTTATTTCTGAAGCAAA
CGCAGGCCACGAACATCAGAGATCGTGTATAAATGCTGCCAGCAGCTTCCCTGAAAGCGAGCTGCGGCGTATCTGAGGAAGCCTAGCCAGCGGGATGAAAGGATGAACATAAACATCGCTTCCGAC
ACAAAAAAGTAGAAAAATGCTGATCAGTACGTTCTGGCTGATACGCTTCTCGGGATCCGTCACAGCATGTTGGAATGGATGACACTGCTTAGAAAAATCAGGGGCTCACCCTCAGTACGGCAGCTTCC
CACAGAGGGTGAAGCCTCAGAAGGAGTCTGACTGCTCTCAATCCATTGGGCGAGATAGGAGTTGGCAAACTGACAGAGCAGGCGGATTTCCGAGGGTACGAGGCTCCCGGGGGAGGTTCTCAAAA
ATCCAGGTTGAGTACGACGCGATGAGCGTACGAGCTATCAGTGGCGAAAGTGAACAACTTCCCGATATTTCCGTAAGTCGCAAGGCGGATCGGAGGAAAGCATGAATCTTACGATTTACAGCGGAA
GAGT***CTCTCTTAAAGG*TAGCCAAATGCCCTCATCTAA**TAGTACGCGCATGAATGGATTAACGAGATTTCCCACTGCTCCCT

B. forskalii shifted and normal R2 insertion site

ATCTACTATCTAGCGAAACCACAGCAAGGGAACGGGCTTGGCATAATCAGCGGGGAAAGAAAGCCTGTTGAGCTTACTGACTGACTTGTGAAAAGACATGAAGGGTGTAGCATAAATGGGAGCGTAAAGC
GACATTGAAAATACCACTACTTTTCTGTTTTTACTTAACTTTCGGTGAAGCGGAAAGCAGGTGCAAGCTCACCCTCTAGATTTAAGCCGACCTTTCCGAGCGGATGATCCGAGCGGAGACAGTCAAGTGGGA
GTTTGGCTGGGCGGCACATCTGTCAAACGATACCGAGGTCTCAAGTGAAGTCAAGAGAACGAAATCTTGTAGAACAAAAGGTTAAAGGCTCACTTGAATTTGATTTTCAATGATTAACAACTGCG
AAAGCATG

Figure S3: Nucleotide sequence of *Beroe forskalii* R2 annotated to show likely start codon (red), coding sequence (green) and stop codon (red). R2 target sites are in bold and underlined. The normal and shifted insertion sites are denoted by asterisks (black and red, respectively). 5' rDNA is in blue.

Supplementary Figure 4

SI Figure 4.1: Topology only (branch length ignored) phylogenetic tree of all site-specific R2s with a protein coding region rooted with human L1 (MFP model finder, 1000 bootstraps, support values under 70 shown). Coloured circles indicate the number of N-terminal zinc fingers. R2s without a coloured circle indicate the element has a partial ORF.

SI Figure 4.2: Phylogenetic tree of site-specific and site-non-specific R2-homologous RT domains rooted with human L1 (MFP model finder, 1000 bootstraps, support values below 70 are shown). Coloured circles indicate the number of N-terminal zinc fingers.

SI Figure 4.3: Phylogenetic tree of site-specific and site-non-specific R2-homologous trimmed ORFs (>900 amino acids) rooted with human L1 (MFP model finder, 2000 bootstraps, all nodes supported with support values over 90). Coloured circles indicate the number of N-terminal zinc fingers.

Supplementary Figure 5

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R2-1_BMi  VDRVTTDAESGLPNHAGANLLQCEWC DRLCKNKAGLTLHKRACKNNPAVGSSAGNTDNR
R2-1_MLe  ITRVRTSSNRG-EHSNGVTYPRCE-----QGVAPLDTHGGICDAPPQVTPATETDKQ-
R2-1_PBa  -----HRCPNCRKLCRSGNGLALHMKHC-----AKCYQNGDNR
R2-1_STig MPEATASAH---SSQRGTAMFVCEHC GKEYRSRSGLSGHRRMH-----FAEGETRAV-
R2-1_MBi  -----ESQIG---YVCPDC GRAFRRSRGMSNHRRTH-----AAAGAVGGR-
R2-1_HBer  -----KSQTG---FPCPDC GRVYRSRSGMSNHRRTH-----LAQEGGDDG-
R2-1_CTe  -----KSQTG---FPCPDC GRVYRSRSGMSNHRRTH-----LAQEGGDDG-
R2-1_ATu  -----DNSTLNIDRRCCGLCGVTFNTKSKLKSH-----ILSRSCSDR-
                                     : *

R2-1_BMi  RINTPP---TMRSLFNCEYCN TGYGTD RGLSAHISKKHIPAWN-----MI
R2-1_MLe  -----KKCEYCEFTYLKPRQIGTHMRKRHPQAWN-----DI
R2-1_PBa  QEPVKP-----R--MECSICGLFFSGQRGVAIHKRKKHPAAWN-----ET
R2-1_STig --PI-----WKCDICQAAFGTKIGLSQHRRQHA EVDN-----QR
R2-1_MBi  -----FSCGICSESF LSKAGLAQHTRHRHPVEHN-----IR
R2-1_HBer  -----FRCDICSAVFRTKAGLGQHTRRQHPVQHN-----IR
R2-1_CTe  -----FRCDICSAVFRTKAGLGQHTRRQHPVQHN-----IR
R2-1_ATu  -----SACKFCGRSFNTFAGVRQHERRVHPLEYASDLQSVIGKASESVIME
                                     * * : : * : *

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Figure S5: Multiple sequence alignment of R2 ORFs with two ZnF N-terminal architecture: Ctenophora: *Bolinopsis microptera*, *Pleurobrachia bachei*, *Mnemiopsis leidyi* (re-curated, first found Kojima 2016). Chondrichthyes: *Mobula birostris*, *Stegostoma tigrinum*, *Hypanus berthallutzae*. Actinopterygii: *Cynodonichthys tenuis*. R2-1_MLe has one ZnF because of an internal truncation. CXXC residues in the ZnFs are highlighted in green.

Supplementary Figure 6

Figure S6: Phylogenetic tree of site-specific R2s constructed with IQTree (R2 ORF, MFP model finder, 1000 replicates with human L1 as an outgroup). Bootstrap values under 60 are shown at nodes. The phylogenetic tree also includes R2s with two N-terminus ZnF R2s in bold text from Kojima et al. 2016.

Supplementary Figure 7

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R2-1_BMi -----KNTMFNITRPEDSQVDRV
R2-1_MLe KLHRCCPLFQEKDSGGLNRSASGVMSNTSHSKLNLKMDNKLKTSLETSPGVRADSIITRV
R2-1_PBa TL----PFLKLNMRNLNNEKNSGAVRSTEFs----VADNRPSQSLRTTESH-----
          . : : .

R2-1_BMi TIDAESGLPNHAGANLLQCEWCDRLCKNKAGLTLHKRACKNNPAVGSAGNTNDNRRINT
R2-1_MLe RTSSNRG-EHSNGVTYPRCE-----QGVAPLDTHGGICDAPPQVTVPATETDKQKK---
R2-1_PBa -----RCPNCRKLCRSGNGLALHMKHC-----AKCYQNGDNRQEPV
          : * * * *
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi PPTMRSLFNCYCYCNTGYGTDRLGSAHISKKHIPEWNMIKMERFKADGPRQHVWREGDWEI
R2-1_MLe -----CEYCEFTYLKPRQIGTHMRKRHPQEWNDIKRTKFLSE-KRQKRWLDEDFEL
R2-1_PBa KPRME---CSICGLFFSGQRGVAIHKRKKHKAPEWNETKRVEDTSL-RKKIRWTSGDREL
          * . * : * : * * : * * * * . . : : * . * * :
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi LCQGEHEDRLPSTAKNKLGVNMFIRASYFPQLTIQAISCQRKSPNFHRY--KNDRLQD
R2-1_MLe LCIGQEEYLVLSIGKQKGINQYIQTQYFPTLSTDAIKSQRKSRRFSEYSEKRSRELQP
R2-1_PBa LHLGMIWEASAETHSQ----EDWVRDHKFPERTINSIKCQIRSKLFRRYVAARPRDEAP
          * * * . . : : : : * * : : * . * * : * * . * :
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi PVTEPQPELEPIPEIEIPAQASNPNTNPLEFTPLAEDIAEIRGKPLGPEILNVYRLLAQ
R2-1_MLe CNTSSDPE-----ELPNEAVT-ENSPLSFDPLDRDVKKISSKDHGDQILLVQEHILN
R2-1_PBa ---APTPE-AAIQEDEC-----AGSILC---LKDAAIRWLEKPEPDGEEYLAIERLQD
          . * * * * . . * * * : : * * : . * :
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi AQFNEANDKSRFIFDELAKDFTRLSTVPKQPTTSKNKNKKKVGKKRISQRPEKRLSPSK
R2-1_MLe GRYQEANTLAKAIFEKLSGKFPNLKTGDHRP--GKQQTARKVGGKRV--RGSGKLSPSK
R2-1_PBa GRLGEAGERSRRKFDLASKYT-----PLAKSQPAKGRSKPVDLKSKTNGKLSPAK
          . : * * . : : * : * : . . * . : : : * : : * * : * * : *
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi AKRKELYAIVQKWH-TKKRSSVIDTILRDSLQGV---REPAHTPEQLAEFWKGLFSRES
R2-1_MLe QNRRELYAIVQKWR-TKKRSKVINQILTNLKE---QSYTHTPDQLAQFWSTLFGRVs
R2-1_PBa RRRRAKYGCQKQKWHNNNQRSGLIRSILQKFGSKEVLKDPRETEETI-DFWSGIFNRDS
          . * : * . * * : * : : * * * * . . . . . : . * : : * * : * * *
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi PPDNRPIPNPRTIEPQLDNPILVSEVTDLSKRATEKATGLDGVPLKHLREIGATALTILY
R2-1_MLe PRDDRPINHRRSVIPELDPLSVVEEVAALKGAKDAATGIDGVPISHLKLHLSAALITILY
R2-1_PBa TPDSREIENARETIGALDNMITVEEVAKALKGKSERARGPDGVPKCLKELGATKLAILEY
          . * . * * : * * * * : * * * * : * * * * * . * : : : * : * *
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi NGLYCKQLIPTSWKEARTVLIPKCDVPSSPGEYRPITISSYYRIYTSIGRRLSDSVGL
R2-1_MLe NGLYVTGSIPDPWKRARTILIPKSNPPASPGDYRPISISSYFYRIYTSISKRLASAVSL
R2-1_PBa NGVFACTSEVPDSWREARTVLIPKKEPKGPADYRPITIGSYFYRAYTSVLGGRISDVVRP
          * * : . : * . * : * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * *
          . : : : :

R2-1_BMi SNRQKGFIAKDGIRDNLILLETIIEDSKKTSPLHMTFMDVVKAFDVSVSHSIRRALEWA
R2-1_MLe DDRQKGFIEDGIRDNLISLIDTLINETKAGSKSLFMTFMDVVKAFDVSVSHYAIARLEWA
R2-1_PBa SQRQKGFVRSIDGIRDNLCLLDGLIYNSKNRVQPLHMSFMDVVKAFDVSVSHFSIQRMLRWS
          . : * * * * : * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * * *
          . : : : :

```

Figure S7: Multiple sequence alignment of Ctenophora B N-terminal architecture sequences: *Bolinopsis microptera*, *Pleurobrachia bachei*, *Mnemiopsis leidyi* (re-curated, first found Kojima 2016). CXXC residues in the ZnFs are highlighted in green.

Supplementary Figure 8

Figure S8.1: Phylogenetic tree of only R2 RLE domains constructed with IQTree (MFP model finder, 1000 replicates). The number of N-terminal ZnFs is annotated at each node. Bootstraps under 50 are shown. Aves branch is collapsed.

Supplementary Figure 9

Figure S9: Cofolding ZnFs are a feature shared among R2 A-lineage and expected for some Utopia. Protein segments that encode for cofolding ZnFs are displayed, which correspond to ZnF3:2 in the experimental structure of PlaMe (R2Pm) and ZnF2:1 of all Utopia elements indicated (AlphaFold models, AF). Individual protein folds are coloured according to the phyla discussed in the main text. Structural alignments for each row relative to R2Pm ZnF3:2 fold are made on the right (boxed), where the top panel includes three structures and the bottom alignment a total of four. The names of the host species not provided in the main text include those annotated by us, *Crossaster papposus* (Cpa), *Phenganax stokvisi* (Pha), and those previously annotated [3-4] *Phytophthora sojae* (PS), *Heliconius melpomene* (HMM), *Chrysemys picta bellii* (CPB).

Supplementary Figure 10

Figure S10.1: Position-specific scoring matrix scores of Aves R2 RTs compared to BoMo (*B. mori*) (lineage D R2) and TaGu (*T. gutatta*) (lineage A R2) RTs. Green shading indicates the R2 has 3 N-terminal ZnFs.

Figure S10.2: Position-specific scoring matrix scores of reptilian (excluding aves) R2 RTs compared to BoMo (*B. mori*) (lineage D R2) and TaGu (*T. gutatta*) (lineage A R2) RTs. Green shading indicates the R2 has 3 N-terminal ZnFs, purple has 1 N-terminal ZnF.

Figure S10.3: Position-specific scoring matrix scores of Actinopterygii, Chondrichthyes, and Amphibia R2 RTs compared to BoMo (*B. mori*) (lineage D R2) and TaGu (*T. gutatta*) (lineage A R2) RTs. Green shading indicates the R2 has 3 N-terminal ZnFs, purple has 1 N-terminal ZnF, and orange has 2 N-terminal ZnFs.

Figure S10.4: Position-specific scoring matrix scores of Ctenophora, Cnidaria, and Arthropoda R2 RTs compared to BoMo (*B. mori*) (lineage D R2) and TaGu (*T. gutatta*) (lineage A R2) RTs. Green shading indicates the R2 has 3 N-terminal ZnFs, purple has 1 N-terminal ZnF, and orange has 2 N-terminal ZnFs.

Figure S10.5: Position-specific scoring matrix scores of Ctenophora, Porifera, Tunicata and Arthropoda R2 RTs compared to BoMo (*B. mori*) (lineage D R2) and TaGu (*T. gutatta*) (lineage A R2) RTs. Red shading indicates the R2 has 4 N-terminal ZnFs, green has 3 N-terminal ZnFs, purple has 1 N-terminal ZnF, and orange has 2 N-terminal ZnFs.

Supplementary Figure 11

Figure S11: Site-specific conservation of individual residues in lineage D and A R2s superimposed with RT residues from (a) *B. mori* (lineage D) and (b) *Z. albicollis* (lineage A, reconstructed from short-reads). Conservation is shown as high (1-3) to low (4-6).

Supplementary Figure 2

LaMa -----
 NePa -----
 CroHe -----
 DeFu EPSSSKHPVH-TNATMALPD--AYEVPREQKQKADIKKKIYWSYSPFRCNLCDGIM
 AgTri -----AGEGTPEALPPVPGENGGQSPDNIVKVTVPDKNPP---CPCCGTRV
 GaGa ----PESAPVQRTEADTTLPS--ASAPAGEGEPSTRVFLVRLPDSNPP---CPICGDHV
 SPun RPIHPPEESAICVTANESTPQIEYNIIERETDVIPSSSAIVQLPQTNPA---CPFCADRI
 PlaMe EPI-----INGTQK-----TIIQLPNDNPA---CPFCGDHV
 PBlA -----KRERKLDKDEPTIWLDPNKPE---CPYCKEVV

LaMa -----DNITC
 NePa -----ERVPC
 CroHe -----PKHSC
 DeFu STIKELKRHISCKHKTfNLVVFCSKCDKEDA-FHNIACHFAKCNKKIIED---ATFMC
 AgTri NSVVSLLLEHLKGGSHGKRVRFCAKCGKENVNVYHVSICHFPKCKGAEIEK--VPAGEWIC
 GaGa GKPSALAVHLVESHAWADVQYQCTHCEKVSNNKHSILCHIPRCQGRVTD---SDRNWAC
 SPun TTPALLKKHVKGYGKGLLQFQCSKCGRLNENQHSIITHLPKCKGNSIDP---ALGEFHC
 PlaMe GKPSALNVHLKRNHGGREVEFQCSMCNKADPKAHSILCHIPKCKGKVTEE---PTGDWAC
 PBlA GKPTALQKHLTGvHGNQAVTFGCMKQQRKDPRVHAILVHIPKCKGPNIPDARQAQNKHRC
 **** *

LaMa RDCGRAFPsLrSLGMHRHhQHPeeVNEERLELIKKK-----RKQWSKEEDEQLMSTA
 NePa -FCGLTFATKRGLSMHQHRRHPTelNAARLTALPSR-----RGVWTSGEDEALIRLA
 CroHe -PCGSEFGTKRGLAMHRFHCHPAEVNAERLTLPTK-----KLWVTQEEMDGLLRHA
 DeFu RHCDEFRTTKSGVsqHARHRHPKAVNDIRLKIAMPA-----KRSKLWLTLETLMLDLE
 AgTri EVCGRDFTTKIGLgQHKRLAHPLIRNqERIVASQPKETSNRGAHKRCWTKEEEEllIKLE
 GaGa VQCPASFNKKVGLSQHKRHVHPVTRNAERVAGSLSRAGLRPRTRRGCSVEEEElTRLD
 SPun EICNNNFLTksGLSQHKRIrHPLVRNEERIMASQPKENSrGKHKSCWSNDEVEQLKTLF
 PlaMe ETCNKQFNtksGLSQHKRIaHPAIRNqERIAASQPKNSQRGKHNSCWTVEEEEQLLAafN
 PBlA EDCGNQYDTQsGLSQHTRHKHPETRNQRIEEKEKEKGGKRGTHKSCWtQEETEQLALLW
 *** : . :. * ** * * : * *

LaMa DMEWKVGMKKDHLAAIRIKfSHRTLDsIKKRLQHLGWAPPAGQQPQNTPLPARSRPPR
 NePa NDIWPSVTLKKHLYNALMPHFpGRSAEALKKRLQLLQWLP-----
 CroHe NGAWKEGMLKTQIFtSLMPHFpGRSAEAIKKRLQSLKWVP-----ARDNPER
 DeFu ATYKN---SKINMDIQKHfENKtSIQIGEKRRRELREKT-----AKMEKEA
 AgTri AQFEG---NKNINKLIAEHITTKAKQISDKRRLLPKK-----PEVTDKE
 GaGa ALFRG---ARNINQLIAAEMGTklPKQISDKRRQLGLCP-----EQATSGG
 SPun DEFgK---YKDVNKRIANLLPSKTAKQIADKRRLLNLYI-----KSTKTPN
 PlaMe NMFwG---KKNINILISDHIHMKTAKQISEKRRLLGLNK-----NATVTTT
 PBlA EKyEG---HANINKLIQqELHTKTAKQIGEKRRNILEKR-----NNKPEIG
 . : : : : : : :

LaMa RIArASSPPLT---SALAGPLPPSPiGSPPPQAkRRRgALWtNREdSELEEHARRLWkPNM
 NePa -----PL----TPShETLNASAL---SP-----
 CroHe -----NSQPL----HATSGNVAPATLPTPDP-----
 DeFu -----NL-----HIDSDDEIESINKSEDE-----
 AgTri -----PGVCLRRTRAAGSVGTEPGTSQQSQA-----
 GaGa -----DA-----ESTSVEEEEsvTPEVET-----
 SPun -----PI-----EPET--QEVtIPENRES-----
 PlaMe -----NP-----LPVS---STChLKIRt-----
 PBlA -----EE-----IPKt---KtQsINRQt-----

LaMa LKkSLAEALScIIKGRSAEAIrkRLQkLGISSATMTSREDIDSEAMRDkDIHQTTPCVQP
 NePa -----KALD-----
 CroHe -----SRVD-----
 DeFu -----EHTN-----
 AgTri -----GILD-----
 GaGa -----QSPL-----
 SPun -----SAPV-----
 PlaMe -----DSPN-----
 PBlA -----

LaMa EEDGGYETPTskKEEWRTLLTKALETL-NEARIESDKL-----KL
 NePa ED-----LI---RWKGRMLDAISPnl-SEPRLGTEEL-----LS
 CroHe DQGANIEDPAA---SWRRALLAAAADHF-KEPKLGAGTL-----KQ
 DeFu VPQSDVQI-----RNTRISTHkKSPQI-KDHKDLVERITEIKDCMKNPeyYDCGIGLME
 AgTri NGPGKCHL-----PGRPAAGEKTMEKL-RRHPDKDNGR-----QK
 GaGa KPPGKI-----RKVLAQRARRWL-KKGQDLSdkV-----RE
 SPun --KGLC-----EALQSKARKNLEKESAMKFE-----KD
 PlaMe TTTGLK-----DTYMCKINENIVNQGQIKFD-----SE
 PBlA EKEGLA-----NKFKQTAITLI-QEhRIKNESI-----AR
 :

LaMa MAKGMLEG---TMTREEAAEQLECIT-----
 NePa LVCNLRDG---SLSSEELNARLEAHA-----
 CroHe ITQDLLNG---KISSGECrVLMGEHA-----
 DeFu VITQYIT---ENISTIKPSASVRPTDDPAAPNDATE-IEV-----
 AgTri TSGQRREGLLQAHYQKTIKEGLSAGAINNFPgAFKQLMDGRemRTMINQTAQDCFGCLes
 GaGa VLGAwVEG---QPGIRARVESVSLDVLTSFLGAPSG-----
 SPun FLTNWLDN---MQNVrHLLEETTVDALCNFLPEPKN-----
 PlaMe VISAWMAG---DSNIRSLVESTSLDILSTFLMETPK-----
 PBlA ALHTWLQE---NNNTRQTVekATEEILNNFPRTAG-----

LaMa -----QEFAPLKWKPREKRTGHR--KEPRSNKQIRRARYAHIQRLYKLRKDDAAHSIL
NePa -----ARHFPHLWRPSTKRTQSI--NKP-SARQIRRARYAAIQRLYQTRKDAASSVL
CroHe -----QHWFPHTWKPSSARPEPK--ARQWKTRERRARYAAVQKLYLRRRDAQAQV
DeFu -----PTNVPQNAEPTTASSSHKRNSGHKRYAKRKGYSKEYQTMFLKDKKKIARIVC
AgTri ISQIRTAMRKGNSGKATMEQPARKF-QKWMKDRAIKGNFLRFQFLHLDGRGLAKIIL
GaGa -----PRGAPDKKRP--EKGGSST--TSWMSRRVAKRGVFLKYQRLFGTKRKLADIIL
SPun -----ITKPKKDRRP-VKDRKQA--KSWMKRAKRGVFLKYQRLFGTKRKLADIIL
PlaMe -----PRKKGNNKIT-NKKSQK--KKWMEKRAVKKGFYKRYQHLFETDRCKLASIIL
PBla -----IHNIPKRKTKKPRGPYR--GKWRQKRRIQKLYKQLQELYDKDRAAAAAYIL
 . . . : : * : : * :

LaMa DGKWREAYREKEREVEGVEEHWAQVFETQAK-DGWPQSM--LPPDLSNIKWGLLEPVTAM
NePa NGSWRSAYKNRSTITDDLDSYWSNIFLQPSHEDPT-----PADPPSTPHWSILDPIAT
CroHe SGSWRNAYRGRAPQPKMDQYAEVFETASATDVT-----PPGSPSEIYWSVVGKITPS
DeFu DGAEDMSCQ---IEATEIFDYKKNILENENTKNPKFELSNIVPSEEDFDHLN--RPITF
AgTri DDIECLSCD---ISPSEIYSVFKARWETPGNFAGLGDFK--ITGKADNNAFK--DLITAK
GaGa DGADRAQC---LPLEEVLRAYRGKWEVSESSFEGLGRFG--VRRDADNFAFK--ALITPE
SPun DGTEKFECE---IDPKIVYEAYKNKWESETEFKGLSNFH--SFDVTDNSKIFY--TRISGK
PlaMe DGTERLQCQ---IPLTEILETYKSKWETLTPFEGLGQFK--SHAVADNTAFE--ILLSAK
PBla DGEKKTNC---LPIQEVYQTYKDKWETKTEFKGLQNFH--PWGGTNDNIDLS--NLITGE
 . . : : . : :

LaMa EVEVALRSM-NNTSAGMDKLSAQEVLTWDL---PSLAGLNLVILATERLPSTLATAVTL
NePa EVTSALSSM-KSSATGLDRLSASQLLSDA---NSIGAYFNILLVSLGVPHTLMARITY
CroHe EVANALKGM-RNSAPGLDRITAEELLTDH---PSLAAYYNLMLAAGGPPPEHLACSRTVF
DeFu EITWHLENSNMNATGPDNVGLKELFGLHARDHTILTDLFNILWQTSKVPCEIKRNRSIL
AgTri EIERNVQEMSKSAPGPDGITLGDIVKMDP-GYSRTAELFNLWLTSGEIPDMVGRCSRVL
GaGa EVVKHMMAMASKSAPGPKLTLRDLRRADP-EGDALAELFSLWLTITGTVDPGLKECSRVL
SPun EVQKNIKEMSRKTAPGPDGITVEDLENVDP-DGEILAAFLNLMVAVGIIPDTIKECSRLL
PlaMe EIMKNIKEMNKNASAPGPKVSLRDLLLADP-ECNALEKLFNTWLTITGIIPNSIKECSRLL
PBla EVKEHLQAMCNKTAAGPDNISVKDLKQVLH-VEQKLAELFNLWLTITGQIPNTVVKRSRIL
* : . : * * : : . : * : *

LaMa IPKVEEPS---GPNDYRPIAIISSVIARALHKVLSKRMREQEFESPLQYAFLRQDGCLEAS
NePa VPKTDSPS---GPSEYRPIVSTVLLRAMHKILARRMLATLDFSDLQAFLRQDGLTLDAS
CroHe IPKVENPQ---TPGDYRPIVASTVLRFAHKLAWRLRDLNLQSPFQHGFLQRDGCLEAT
DeFu IPKNVPLDSLGNIGNWRPITIGTALMKLFTKLLTKRLSTFVSIHERQKGFINARGCLENL
AgTri IPKSTKPERLKDINWRPITIGSILLRFLSRIVTARLSKACPLNPRQRFIRAAGCSEN
GaGa IPKTVDRKLGQLGNWRPITIGSIVLRLFSRVLTAARLAAACPINPRQRFIAAPGAENL
SPun IPKTSDEPKLKDIGNWRPLTIGSIIIRLFSRILTIRLAKACPLNARQRFIDSPGCSSEN
PlaMe IPKTADPEALKELGNWRPLTIGSIVLRLFSRIITNRLAKACPLNARQRFIATPGCSSEN
PBla IPKTSDETEKKVGNWRPLTISSVLRFLFSKIMTSRITKACPLNARQRFIAAGCSSEN
 : * : . : * * : : : : * : * :

LaMa ALLHAVLRTAHERTKPLAAAFLDVSKAFDTSVSHNAILGAAEKAGTPPPILRYLNQLYKNA
NePa TILHTILRKVHTELKPLSMMFLDVSKAFDSISHTLIRVATTSGLPAPLLSYLRHLYQTS
CroHe ALLHTILRKVHNSRKSCAMFLDVAKAFDTSVSHQTLFRVAVELGLPPLVNYLKCLYSRS
DeFu NILKNSIKGARKNKDSLAVIFIDISKAFDSVGHKHLNLSLKRHLVPLGYRQLTKDLYTNS
AgTri KLLQTIIRTAKEHKPLGVVFDIAKAFDTSVSHQHILHALQQRGVDPHIIGLVNMYKDI

GaGa KVLELLLRKRKRDRQPLGVVFDLARAQFDSVSHDHISWVLKAKGVDEHIVNLIEDSYQKV
SPun KSLQSIIEYSKKEKQFGVVDIAKAFDSVSHDHIWVLKERVDEHIIKIIQDSYTKV
PlaMe KILHTIVKQAKTSKSLGVVFDIAKAFDSVSHDHIMWVLQERGLDQHVNIIEDSYKKI
PBla WLLHNIKRAKDKKELGVVLDIAKAFDTSVSHDHIRWVLREMGDKHIIQLIMSAYDNA
* . : : . : . : * : * : * : * : *

LaMa KLQL-----GSTTTQCSRGVVRQGDPIPIFILVMGEVLEALPD-VGVRW----GERQ
NePa KIRL-----GTHDSSCGRGRVQGDPLSPILFILAIEDILHRVLP-AGFDL----AATR
CroHe TVRL-----ADKATKCGRGRVQGDPLSPLLFIMVDDIVRKTLP-AGFDL----DGQR
DeFu TTTFKGKNNINTDEIHMKSGVKQGDLSPLLFNIAMDPLICDLQYKCGCSFNNIQGTRO
AgTri STYVTTKRDTHTDKIQIRVGVKQGDPLSPLLFNLAMDPLLCKLEESGKGFHR----GESS
GaGa TTRVQVFNQ-VTPPTISIKTGVKQGDPMSPPLLFNIAMDPLIAKLETDGGQGVK----GSAS
SPun STRLKVSKT-LTDSISLKVGVKQGDPMSPPLLFNLAMDPLINALEEQGEGVQV----EDMK
PlaMe HTRMEVGT-RTPIIEIKVGVKQGDPMSPPLLFNLAMDPLITALEKANTGFSY----GKNK
PBla TTSIKLKEG-NTPDIHRSVGVKQGDPLSPLLFNLAMDPLITELETEGHGVED----ENWT
 . ** : * : * : * : * : * :

LaMa IDSIAYADDLILLAESPRLQRKLDGVCRLQKAGMALNKKSVMTILKDRRKTALALA
NePa IGSIAAYADDLILLAERPERLQKLNILLSAFHADAGLIINSSKSHGLTIAKDGKLLVLL
CroHe VDSLAYADDLILLAESPRQLQKLLHLLSEALRKAGMSLNARKSRGLTITKVKSRKQMVIT
DeFu TTALAFADDIAVLSNSWGMQANLQIEKFSKATGLKLVKTHGFLISHF-GDKIVVYNK
AgTri ITAMAFADDLILLSWENMQNINIKILETFCDLTLGKTQGEKCHGFYIKPT-KDSYTIIN
GaGa LTTLAFADDLILLSWEGMLKNISILEDFCNLTLGLRVQPKKQCGFFLNPT-CDSFTVNN
SPun LKTMAFADDLILLSNFEGMSKNIKILEQFCQTTGLQVQPKKQCGFLITPT-KDSYIINN
PlaMe ITSLAFADDLIVMSDTEWGMNKNIQILETFCNLSGLKVQAKCYGFFLPT-HDSYTIIN
PBla ITTLAFADDIAVMSDCKEMKQNLQIEAFCNLTGLKVQTTKSYGFALQPT-KDSYIVNN
 : * : * : * : * : * : * : * :

LaMa PHQYTTDNGQVPCMGLSDSQRYLGIQFT-WKGRVTPK-QTSELGRMLLEITSAPLKPYQR
NePa PHEYRTGSSTIKPIGPTNITYLGLRFN-WKQQLLPR-HTATLSTMLAEVSAQPLKPYQR
CroHe PTTYECEGEPIKPMGTDSDSVRYLGLHFN-WKGRIVPK-HTGKLDLSELKELKAPLKPYQR
DeFu CKPWLFRSKIEFIHPGESERYLGLNFDPHIGCNTPNALNLKLSWAKKLDLPLKPTQK
AgTri CAAWTINGTPLNMNINPGESEKYLGLQFDPWTGLAKTN-LTTKLEWFLERIDQAPLKPLQK
GaGa CEAWKIAGREITMLGPGESTRYLGLNVGPWVGIDKPD-LGTQLSSWLERIGTAPLKPMQK
SPun CKKWSIEGTEVNMIPGQREKYLGAIDPWTIFAEN-FEEKIEDWLCKLEVAPLKPSQK
PlaMe CDAWKIDKDSLNIQPGSEKYLGLKVDPIWIGFSKPV-LAEKLTIWLRKLEAPLKPSQK
PBla IKPWTIKDQPIQMVQPAHTTRYLGIQVGPWKGMEKPN-MIADTKKWLQNTKAPLKPTQK
 : : : . * * . . : * * * :

LaMa IELVRDFLVPRLHELVLGCAHRNTIARMDRIRRETRTWLRLPKDTSGLFLHSPVKSQG
NePa LEVLRNLYIPKLTHELVLGRAHRNTLKKIDVLIIRAAIRQWLRFPKDTPTAYFHARIQDGG
CroHe LQLLKFHAVPKFTHLVLGHAHRNTVKKLDCLTRAARVRLRPLQDTPGLYLVHANVKGDDG
DeFu IKIFCQYIVPKLSYSLEMTGTANTLVALDQTIKATVKHYLHLPHYINDGLLYSRKKNNGG
AgTri LDILKTYTIPRLTYLADHSEIKAGALEALDQKIRTAVKDWLHLPCTCDAILYSSTKDGG
GaGa LSLLVQYAIPLRNYQADYAGIGRVALEALDSMNRKVKKEWHLFACTSDGLLHSHRDRDGG
SPun LEILNIHTIPRIIYADHTNCNITKLNLDNMIRKRLKDWLHLPASTCHGLFYSKNRDGG
PlaMe LTMLNIYTIPIRIYADHTDTKKTLSSLDDNIRTVVKGWHLHLPDPTCNFITYTKTRDGG
PBla LEILRITYTIPRIIYHNEQTGTGKTKLKDNLIRAGIKSWLHLAHDTCNLITYTKTKDGG
 : . : * : * : * : * : * : * : * :

LaMa	LGIPCLGTTVPLLQKRRFEKLLSSDCPIKQTLTELPFMTTLRRVNL-----	AgTri	CNVENETCAHIIGQCPVTKDARIKRHNHICDMLSEEARKKDWVVFKEPYIRDTTKELYKP
NePa	LGIPALTTQMPFLQHRRFTKLLSSASPSIQSICQEPAFVQAYARVLT-----	GaGa	CTHPRETLGHILGICPSVQEARILRHNKLCILAAEGKKCEWTVYEPHLRNAAGELRKP
CroHe	LGIPCFCSTSIPLLQKRRFEKIATNPATIFQIMQRQDSFRQTGRRLDK-----	SPun	CKAKFETCSHILGQCPTLQEARIKRHNKLCITLLKEEAKKLEWVFDEPHLNRAGELRKP
DeFu	LSIPKCTCSIGINKVNNLLYLRESTDVCITNSFLYAGIV-----IN	PlaMe	CTASYESLSHILGQCPAVQGARIRRNKLCMSLKREAKELKWVVYEEPHLHTEKELRKP
AgTri	LGVTKLAGLIPSVQARRLHRIAQSDETMKEFLEKQDMEQLYRKLWVQAGGEREEIPSIW	PBlA	CPAKYESLSHILGQCPGLQNAIRIWRHNAIGKLLANQAKKKKWTVHQEPHLRNKDNQLRKP
GaGa	LGLPRLAKAIPAEQVRRILRVATSSDEVTRKVSYACGISDEVERLWLAGGDMSSVPRFE		. * : ** * : * ** : : : ** : : **
SPun	LGIPRLERLIPSVQARSLHRISQSSDYKIMNIAFSCGLESEFEKKWVQAGGAKETRPNLK	LaMa	DLLVDTGKRIIILDVTVAEPR---MEQSHQLKSSKYGSPDNTAAIVAWTG--TKVPIKH
PlaMe	LGVTRLASLIPSIQARRLHRIATSEDETIRNIAMANNIEEEFQNLWVTAGGKKEEIPRIT	NePa	DILVESAGKLIIVMDVSVIAGHR---LPETWNLKTSKYGSNQATQDLQRWHN--SLISIKH
PBlA	LGITRLETTLPHQRNCTLLKIINSPDLTTRTIARALGIEEQFSKWWKKAGGSEDNKPKIY	CroHe	DLIIETDQTQYVLVDSVAVAGR---MTESWDIKVEKYGRPDRVEAIRKWAIPATKRVEH
	*.: . : : : . : :	DeFu	DLILTNNHTAHVVDVSIRYETSAGSLESAFEQKVSYYSS--ELMSAIQQHTK---CSQVAF
		AgTri	DLIFVKDGHAFVVDVTVRYETTTTSLLEAAAQKVNKYK--HLETEVRNLTN---AKDVVF
LaMa	-----PCRVRNEIV-----CSSKEAQVEWEKIWRTSAD	GaGa	DLIFVVDGTALVVDVTVRYEKDSASLSAAAADKAAKYL--GLNAIQIQLTG---AEHVTY
NePa	-----P---TLPIF-----ESKSAIKQHWADQLQSID	SPun	DVILVKDKKALVVDVTVRFEYKEDGLRKAKEKASYSS--DLTEPIIETLK---AKKVNY
CroHe	-----PCRLNSTVV-----TSKTEVREEWGNMNSNSVD	PlaMe	DLIFVKEEMALVVDVTVRFEYKEKVFEDAAAQKVRHYK--DLTSQIKELTG---AKEIEY
DeFu	DVIDEIIKTHH-----LHILHA-ECLNMSLELTASY----NWRESEFNRWKDM---VVQ	PBlA	DYIIFTKERTAMVVDITVRWEGKMGLEEAQEKIKYYE--ELRDTIQKEWG---VKDISF
AgTri	E----ALPTSEQSNRG--DTTSEWEAPILKPKFKPKC---DWRKKEFEKWTKL---VSQ		* : . : : : : : : * * : : .
GaGa	D----PEAPRSPGVQGPCEAAQEIPSVVRKLAIPRPS---NWRAEEHSHKWAQL---SCQ	LaMa	VPVVLSSRGLLYGPGSRGLRTMGLTSRDLCD----LCLLAVAGSLKCYDAYTRGT-----
SPun	DILPPPPEPKY-----YEKLNEWKPKLKIKFPLPL---NYRKEEFREWAKL---KCQ	NePa	VPVVISARGLLFNKSGQGLRDLGLTRRDISD----ICLLSIIIGSLKSYDLYKRGTLDDFR
PlaMe	D----PVSIDYRLPRRILELLNEWKPAKPKMYPIPC---NWREAEMAHWKNL---PCQ	CroHe	LPVIVSNRGLCYQPSGDGLRALGLTSRDISD----LCLLAIISGSLRCYDLYMRGTRAV--
PBlA	P-----QPQNTTQKPKTEKEEIPVTTKIQPTHKKKEAEWAKL---PCQ	DeFu	HGFIVGCRGTWPTCNLNDLKLGIQYPNPFK--KNICFTTMDTLKMFQIFMDN-----
	. * . :	AgTri	MGFPLGARGKWTGNFELLNLTGLSKSRQVRVAKTLSTVALLSSVDIVHMFASRRVQ-
		GaGa	FGLPIGARGKWHADNGEVLSELGLSRKERVARLLSWRALLGSVDMVNFASKHRQETL
LaMa	GRSGVNEVDVPSYTWVGKPRRVFPRILHRLGIQLRGGTLNTKARASRGRETAPSIDIACRG	SPun	FGLPIGARGKWPENNNLLRELGMEEGRVKRLARLFLSRLTLLYSTNMLHMFENIGKGQKA
NePa	GRDLAQTIDIVASHWWIQHPENVFPRHLRLGLQLRGGLLSTKTRNNRGPTRQ-ANVSCVG	PlaMe	FGFPLGARGKWPENNEKVLTAIGMPDYQKQRTAKRFSKRTLLYSIDVINTFENIGKNNK-
CroHe	GRELRHPEVDKASHEWLLRPDRVFPRLHMRGIQLRGGLLPTKARSGRGNRQVTSKTCRG	PBlA	HGFVCGARGKWPQDNFGILTCLGIESHRLDGLAKLFSRRTVQYSCRMLHTFERDKKNQTG
DeFu	GDGVQYYQNNACSNYLWMLKPKNMKENQYIAALKLRANIPDTRTLTRGR-NR-QFSNCRY		. . ** . * : * : . : : : . :
AgTri	GRGISSFKNDSISNDWLQYRRIPHRKLITALQLRANVYPTREFLSRGREEN-STKACRH	LaMa	-----
GaGa	GEGVELFRNDPVSNGWINGRGLAERLRIVALKLRNSVYPTREFLGRGM-AG-TNVGCRH	NePa	RTKPR---SGIG
SPun	GSGIQHFQDDIISNNWLRINKGITEKQFILALKLRANVFPTRREFLGRGT-QN-ANRACRH	CroHe	-----
PlaMe	GSGIEHFNDNTISNDWLQFHRGFSERQFLMGLKIRANVYPTREYQGRGR-TN-KNVNCRN	DeFu	-----
PBlA	GGAVENFINDSISNDWIRYKDMTEKEFITAIKLRNTNYPTREFLARGK-EN-YERKCRK	AgTri	-----DSG-
	* : * * : . . : : : * . * : ** *	GaGa	LDDAPACVEHVA
		SPun	Y-----FVNSNL
LaMa	ACHARETLNHILQICEVTHDARCARHNRIAKLLEKMLRRRVDRTWIEPIIP-TQKSFIPK	PlaMe	-----NNVP
NePa	ACRMPEINHLIQCEKTHDARCARHNRMKKNVQLLRAKGLKSWMEPIIP-TSTTFMKP	PBlA	HVDC-----
CroHe	ACQNVETLNLHLIQCDVTHDARCARHNRLHRLERLLHKKGLRRTTLEPVIP-AGSSFIPK		
DeFu	CMDVGETISHISGSCPCTKDIRRRHNKILELLIERAKRCGWIAYREPHLRNPNGELRKP		

Figure S12: Multiple sequence alignment of R2 proteins selected for activity testing: LaMa (*L. marequensis*, Largescale yellowfish), NePa (*N. papilliferus*, killifish), DeFu (*D. fucus*, Northern dusky salamander), CroHe (*C. o. helleri*, Southern Pacific Rattlesnake), PBlA (*P. blainvillii*, Blainville's Horned Lizard), SPun (*S. punctatus*, Tuatara), GaGa (*G. gangeticus*, Gharial crocodile), AgTri (*A. tricolor*, Tricoloured blackbird) and PlaMe (*P. megacephalum*, Big-headed turtle). Myb2 domain highlighted in orange. N-terminal ZnFs annotated with red asterisk.

Supplementary Figure 13

Figure S13: Related to Fig. 4b-c. Immunoblot of affinity purified R2 proteins resolved from FLAG affinity by 8% SDS-PAGE. Asterisks denote background bands from flag antibody purification beads. LaMa (*L. marequensis*, Largescale yellowfish), NePa (*N. papilliferus*, killifish), CroHe (*C. o. helleri*, Southern Pacific Rattlesnake), DeFu (*D. fucus*, Northern dusky salamander), PBla (*P. blainvillii*, Blainville's Horned Lizard), SPun (*S. punctatus*, Tuatara), GaGa (*G. gangeticus*, Gharial crocodile), and PlaMe (*P. megacephalum*, Big-headed turtle), AgTri (*A. tricolor*, Tricolored blackbird), and TaGu (*T. guttata*, Zebra finch)

Supplementary Methods

Supplementary Figure 14

Figure S12: Overview of the R2 discovery pipeline. A sensitive online BLASTN and TBLASTN search was used to find the presence of R2s in the species of interest. Based on the outcome of the search, the R2 was either categorised as full-length or flagged for follow-up using the truncated/misassembled pipeline. Species were removed from further analysis if there is no significant match to R2s. For a truncated or misassembled R2, a subset of long reads and short reads were downloaded from the SRA database. Long reads were made into a BLASTN database to find R2-containing reads. R2-containing reads were error-corrected with short reads using Ratatosk. The error-corrected R2-containing long reads were made into a BLASTN database. Using a subset of R2 query sequences, a sensitive local BLASTN search was performed. Sequences that exceed 4200 nucleotides and contain the required 28s rRNA flanking target sites were selected for ORF translation. Finally, the R2 sequences that fulfil all the requirements (28S rRNA flanks, ORFs, domains) were categorised as full-length R2s.

Downloading long reads from SRA database and sensitive BLASTN search

```
#!/bin/bash
#configure to your HPC requirements
#Required tools
#BLAST+, SRA-Toolkit, seqtk, fastqc

#Download long reads
wget https://sra-LONG-READS
#Convert SRR to fastq
fastq-dump SRR-LONG-READS

#Convert fastq to fasta
seqtk seq -a LONG-READS.fastq > LONG-READS.fasta

#Run fastqc on data
#fastqc LONG-READS.fasta
#Concatenate fasta if there are multiple
#cat *LONG-READS.fasta > LONG-READS-COMBINED.fasta

#Make blast database using long reads
makeblastdb -in LONG-READS.fasta -dbtype nucl -out LONG-READS_db
#Sensitive blast search using R2 query sequences
blastn -query R2-QuerySeqs.fasta -db LONG-READS_db -word_size 7 -outfmt "6 qseqid
sseqid sseq pident length mismatch gapopen qstart qend sstart send evaluate bitscore"
> LONG-READS_best_matches

#Extract best hits as fasta file
awk '{print ">"$2"\n"$3}' LONG-READS_best_matches > seqs.fasta
```

Downloading short reads from SRA database and de novo assembly of R2s

```
#!/bin/bash
#configure to your HPC requirements

#Required tools
#BWA, SAMtools, SPAdes, SRA-Toolkit, fastqc

#Download short reads
wget https://sra-SHORT-READS

#Convert SRR to fastq
fastq-dump --split-e SHORT-READS

#Run fastqc on data
#fastqc SHORT-READS_1.fastq SHORT-READS_2.fastq

#Index R2 query sequence
bwa index R2-QuerySeqs.fasta

#Map short read sequences to query file
bwa mem R2-QuerySeqs.fasta SHORT-READS_1.fastq SHORT-READS_2.fastq > aln.sam

#Convert sam to bam
samtools sort -O BAM -o aln.bam aln.sam

#Index bam file
samtools index aln.bam

#Extract mapped reads
samtools view -F 4 -b -o mapped.bam aln.bam

#Convert mapped reads to fastq file
samtools fastq mapped.bam > mapped.fastq

#Make spades directories
mkdir spades_denovo
makdir spades_ts

#De novo assembly of R2 mapped reads with Spades denovo and with trusted contigs
options
spades.py --12 mapped.fastq -o spades_denovo
spades.py --12 mapped.fastq --trusted-contigs R2-QuerySeqs.fasta -o spades_ts
```

Downloading long and short reads from SRA database and error correction prior sensitive BLASTN search

```
#!/bin/bash
#configure to your HPC requirements

#Required tools
#BLAST+, BWA, SAMtools, SPAdes, SRA-Toolkit, fastqc

#Download short reads
wget https://sra-SHORT-READS

#Download long reads
wget https://sra-long-READS

#Convert SRR to fastq
fastq-dump --split-e SHORT-READS
fastq-dump SRR-LONG-READS

#Run fastqc on data
fastqc SHORT-READS_1.fastq SHORT-READS_2.fastq
fastqc LONG-READS.fasta

#Concatenate long reads
cat *.fastq > LONG-READS.fastq

#Create a list file containing short read headers named short_reads.lst

#Error correct long reads with short reads with Ratatosk
Ratatosk correct -v -c 32 -s short_reads.lst -l LONG-READS.fastq -o
corrected_LONG-READS

#Convert fastq to fasta
seqtk seq -a LONG-READS.fastq > LONG-READS.fasta

#Make blast database using error-corrected long reads
makeblastdb -in LONG-READS.fasta -dbtype nucl -out LONG-READS_db
#Sensitive blast search using R2 query sequences
blastn -query R2-QuerySeqs.fasta -db LONG-READS_db -word_size 7 -outfmt "6 qseqid
sseqid sseq pident length mismatch gapopen qstart qend sstart send evalue bitscore"
> LONG-READS_best_matches

#Extract best hits as fasta file
awk '{print ">"$2"\n"$3}' LONG-READS_best_matches > seqs.fasta
```

Plotting the evolutionary rate of individual residues

```
# Load libraries
library(ggplot2)
#Create MSA of aligned RT sequences
#Use IQTree to run site-specific algorithm
http://www.iqtree.org/doc/Advanced-Tutorial
#Extract the output file with site rates mapped to individual positions in the MSA

# Define sequence
sequence <- unlist(strsplit("YOUR-RT-SEQ-OF-INTEREST-FROM-MSA", NULL))

# Read site rates from the CSV file
numbers <- read.csv("~/site-rates.csv")

# Set this to TRUE if you want to filter out dashes in MSA, or FALSE if you want to
keep
filter_dashes <- TRUE

# Create a data frame mapping positions, residues, and numbers
mapping <- data.frame(
  Position = seq_along(sequence),
  Residue = sequence,
  Number = numbers$Number
)

# Apply the dash filter conditionally
if (filter_dashes) {
  mapping <- mapping %>%
    filter(Residue != "-") %>%
    mutate(Position = seq_along(Residue))
}

# Split residue plot into three rows
mapping <- mapping %>%
  mutate(Group = ceiling(seq_along(Residue) / (n() / 3)))

# Custom colours
subdued_palette <- c("#2F7AC6", "#4D9DC6", "#7EC0B8", "#A7D2A0", "#D1E0A8",
"#F2F4B0")

# Plot using ggplot2
ggplot(mapping, aes(x = Position, y = 1, fill = Number)) +
  geom_tile() +
  geom_text(aes(label = Residue), family = "Courier", size = 3, color = "black") +
  scale_fill_gradientn(colors = subdued_palette) + # Use custom subdued gradient
  scale_x_continuous(breaks = mapping$Position, labels = mapping$Residue) +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(
    axis.title.y = element_blank(),
```

```
axis.text.y = element_blank(),
axis.ticks.y = element_blank(),
panel.grid = element_blank(),
axis.text.x = element_text(family = "Courier", size = 5, vjust = 1),
axis.ticks.x = element_line(),
axis.title.x = element_text(vjust = -0.5)
) +
facet_wrap(~ Group, nrow = 3, scales = "free_x") +
labs(title = "Protein Sequence Mapping", x = "Residue", fill = "Number")

ggsave(file = "~/sites.svg")

print(mapping)
```

Plotting PSSM charts

```
# Load libraries
if (!requireNamespace("ggrepel", quietly = TRUE) | !requireNamespace("ggforce",
quietly = TRUE)) {
  install.packages(c("ggrepel", "ggforce"))
}
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(ggrepel)
library(ggforce)

#Run PSSM using PSIBlast for RTs of interest using 1) BoMo then 2) TaGu RTs as the
query
#Create csv: R2 IDs, corresponding bitscores, common species group, number of
N-terminal ZnFs
#For example:
#ID_Code, BoMo, TaGu, ZnF_No, Common.Group
#R2-1_OL, 150, 400, 3, Fish (Bony)

# Load data
df <- read.csv("~/PSSMscores.csv")
str(df)

# Validate columns
required_cols <- c("BoMo", "TaGu", "Common.Group", "ID_Code", "ZnF_No")
if (!all(required_cols %in% colnames(df))) stop("Required columns are missing.")

# Prepare the data
df_filtered <- df %>%
  select( BoMo = BoMo, TaGu = TaGu, ZnF_No, Common.Group, ID_Code) %>%
#Enter common group you want to plot, e.g. "Fish (Bony)"
  filter(Common.Group %in% c("Common.Group of interest"))
if (nrow(df_filtered) == 0) stop("The filtered data frame is empty.")

#Filter any R2s from the plot if needed
#Filter the data frame to remove rows where 'label' is in 'labels_to_remove'
df_filtered <- df_filtered %>%
  filter(!Code %in% c("R2-1_Example"))

# Variables for axes
x_var <- "TaGu"
y_var <- "BoMo"
# Create the PSSM plot
ggplot(df_filtered, aes_string(x = x_var, y = y_var, color = "Common.Group")) +
  geom_point(show.legend = FALSE) + # Remove legend for points
  #geom_point(position = position_jitter(width = 0.2, height = 0.2), show.legend =
FALSE) + # Remove legend for jittered points
  # Draw hulls based on ZnF_No, ignoring Common.Group: this groups and colour codes
R2s based on the number of N-terminal zinc fingers and not common species group
```

```

geom_mark_hull(aes(group = ZnF_No, fill = ZnF_No),
               concavity = 10, expand = unit(2.5, "mm"),
               alpha = 0.15, colour = "black", size = 0.0, show.legend = FALSE) +
# Remove legend for hulls
# Colour code for each species group
labs(x = x_var, y = y_var) + # No legend for color and fill
geom_text_repel(aes(label = Code), size = 3) +
theme_minimal() +
theme(
  panel.grid.major = element_line(),
  panel.grid.minor = element_line(),
  axis.line = element_line(color = "black", size = 0.3) # Keep axis lines
) +
scale_color_manual(values = c(
  "Fish (Bony)" = "#76B49E", "Tunicata" = "#6495EC", "Arthropoda" = "#B196FF",
  "R/Bird" = "#6B8E22", "Echinodermata" = "#4169E1", "R/Snake" = "#FFBF00",
  "R/Lizard" = "#E97929", "R/Crocodile/Alligator" = "#9ACD31", "Cnidaria" =
"#5661D6",
  "Ctenophora" = "#271F5B", "Fish (Cartilaginous)" = "#87CEEB", "R/Turtle" =
"#E0E41D",
  "Amphibian" = "#008080", "Mollusca" = "#B65090", "Annelida" = "#E08BE0",
  "Platyhelminthes" = "#DFB0FF", "R/Lizard (Like)" = "#AE3E0D", "Porifera" = "red"
)) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c("A" = "#0B8731", "D" = "#2B10FF", "B" = "#FC8D62",
"C" = "#FC8D62"))

ggsave(filename = "fishesPSSM.svg", width = 10, height = 10, path = "~/your-path")

```

Supplementary Figure 15

Figure S15: Phylogenetic tree of R2s constructed with RaxML rooted with human L1 ORF2 (R2 trimmed amino acid sequence, model JTT, 1000 replicates). Bootstrap values under 80 are shown at nodes.

SI References:

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2. Wilkinson ME, Frangieh CJ, Macrae RK, Zhang F. Structure of the R2 non-LTR retrotransposon initiating target-primed reverse transcription. *Science.* 2023. Available from: <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.adg7883>
3. K. K. Kojima, Y. Seto, H. Fujiwara, The Wide Distribution and Change of Target Specificity of R2 Non-LTR Retrotransposons in Animals. *PLOS ONE* 11, e0163496 (2016).
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